

A Simple, Swift and Sensitive UV-Spectrophotometric Method for Estimating Water Insoluble Pioglitazone Hydrochloride in Solid Dosage Forms

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ABSTRACT

This study focuses on the development and validation of a UV spectrophotometric method for the estimation of pioglitazone hydrochloride (PIO) in pharmaceutical dosage forms. The method involves measuring absorbance at 268 nm for PIO. Its validation was performed following ICH guidelines, addressing parameters such as specificity, linearity, range, precision, accuracy, detection limit, quantification limit, and robustness. The method showed excellent linearity in the concentration range of 3.74–56.07 µg/ml, with correlation coefficients nearing 0.999. Precision tests yielded low % RSD values, indicating strong repeatability and minimal variability within and between days. For this very low aqueous solubility drug, accuracy was verified through recovery experiments, with results falling within the 98–102% range. The method also demonstrated good sensitivity, as reflected by low LOD and LOQ values. Robustness studies confirmed the method's reliability under varied analytical conditions. Application to tablet formulations verified its effectiveness for accurate drug quantification. Overall, this UV spectrophotometric method provides a straightforward, sensitive, and economical approach for the routine analysis and swift quality control of PIO-containing tablet formulations.

Keywords: UV Spectrophotometry, Method development, Method validation, and pioglitazone hydrochloride.

INTRODUCTION

Pioglitazone hydrochloride is an oral antidiabetic agent belonging to the thiazolidinedione (TZD) class, primarily used in the management of type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM)^[1]. It is marketed under various brand names and is commonly prescribed either as monotherapy or in combination with other antidiabetic drugs such as metformin, sulfonylureas, or insulin^[2]. Pioglitazone improves glycaemic control by targeting insulin resistance, a central defect in type 2 diabetes^[3]. Pioglitazone hydrochloride (PIO) is a synthetic compound classified under the thiazolidinedione group of antidiabetic agents. Chemically, it is known as **5-[4-[2-(5-ethylpyridin-2-yl)ethoxy]benzyl]thiazolidine-2,4-dione hydrochloride**. The molecular structure of pioglitazone includes a thiazolidinedione ring, which is essential for its pharmacological activity, particularly its ability to enhance insulin sensitivity^[4]. This structure is linked via a benzyl group to an

ethoxy side chain containing a substituted pyridine ring, specifically a 5-ethylpyridin-2-yl moiety as shown in the figure.1

Figure 1: Structure of Pioglitazone hydrochloride.

Mechanism of Action

Pioglitazone acts as a selective agonist for the peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma (PPAR-γ), a nuclear receptor predominantly expressed in adipose tissue, skeletal muscle, and the liver^[5]. Activation of PPAR-γ regulates the transcription of insulin-responsive genes involved in glucose and lipid metabolism^[6]. This leads to

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enhanced insulin sensitivity in peripheral tissues and decreased hepatic glucose production^[7-8].

By modulating adipocyte differentiation and promoting the uptake of fatty acids and glucose, pioglitazone reduces circulating free fatty acids and improves lipid profiles, contributing to overall metabolic homeostasis^[9-10]. Unlike some other oral hypoglycemics, pioglitazone does not stimulate insulin secretion, thereby posing a lower risk of hypoglycemia when use as monotherapy^[11].

In addition to its glucose-lowering effects, pioglitazone has shown benefits in reducing markers of inflammation, improving endothelial function, and potentially providing cardiovascular protection,

although these effects remain an area of ongoing research^[12-13].

Numerous studies have reported the development and validation of UV spectrophotometric methods for the estimation of pioglitazone hydrochloride (PIO) in pharmaceutical dosage forms, highlighting the method's simplicity, sensitivity, and suitability for routine analysis. Some method have demonstrated that UV spectrophotometry offers reliable quantification of PIO using absorbance maxima typically around 269 nm. This comparative overview demonstrates the versatility of UV spectrophotometry for pioglitazone analysis across different formulations and analytical contexts as shown in table 1

Table 1: Comparative Study of Reported UV Spectrophotometric Methods for Pioglitazone Hydrochloride

Author(s)	Sample Matrix	λ_{max} (nm)	Solvent Used	Validation Parameters Covered
Patel et al.[14]	Tablet	269 nm	Methanol	Linearity, accuracy, precision, LOD, LOQ
Rote & Bari [15]	Bulk & Tablet	269 nm	0.1N NaOH	Linearity, precision, recovery, LOD, LOQ, solution stability
Nanda & Gaikwad [16]	Tablet	269 nm	0.1N NaOH	Accuracy, repeatability, robustness, precision, LOD, LOQ
Basavaiah et al.[17]	Bulk	520 nm (colorimetric)	Dye-based	Linearity, reproducibility
Tavallali & Sheikhaei [18]	Bulk	570 nm (colorimetric)	Ninhydrin	Precision, stability, stoichiometry
Bhatt et al. [19]	Tablet	269 nm	Methanol	All ICH parameters
Kadam et al.[20]	Tablet (PIO + Glimepiride)	265 nm	Methanol	Simultaneous estimation
Mehta et al. [21]	Tablet (PIO + Metformin)	265 nm	Methanol	Absorbance correction method
Agrawal et al. [22]	Tablet	266 nm	Methanol: Water (1:1)	Linearity, accuracy
Sastry & Naidu [23]	Bulk & Tablet	267 nm	Methanol	Repeatability, linearity
Gowrisankar & Reddy [24]	Tablet	267 nm	Methanol	Precision, range
Bharathi & Reddy [25]	Pharmaceutical dosage forms	269 nm	Methanol	Validation parameters as per ICH guidelines
Patel, R. M. et al.[26]	Tablets (PIO + Metformin)	269 nm	Methanol: Water (80:20)	Simultaneous estimation, validation parameters
Siddiqui, M. R. et al. [27]	Review article	Various	Various	Comprehensive overview of analytical methods

Overall, the literature supports UV spectrophotometry as a cost-effective and efficient method for the quantification of pioglitazone in both bulk and tablet forms. The proposed techniques offer several advantages, including straightforward standard and sample preparation, a wide concentration range, and high sensitivity. Additionally, all the methods have been validated following ICH guidelines [28].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Chemicals and Reagents

Samples of PIO API was arranged from approved vendors and applied as a working standard. The formulation products were purchased from the local medical shop. The other analytical consumables like Acetonitrile and water were procured from local distributors.

Instrumentation

A UV-Visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-1900i) equipped with 1 cm matched quartz cuvettes and automatic wavelength correction was employed for the analysis. Absorption spectra for both standard and sample solutions were recorded within the 200–400 nm wavelength range using a 1 cm quartz cell. A Mettler Toledo digital balance was used for precise weighing of samples, and an ultrasonic bath was utilized to sonicate the tablet solution for complete dissolution.

Method development

Selection of solvent

Pioglitazone (PIO) demonstrated good solubility in acetonitrile and in the mixture of acetonitrile and water at 40:60 ratio. The selection of the solvent was based on several factors, including the solubility of the analytes, cost-effectiveness, and the method's overall suitability. The mixture of acetonitrile and water at 40:60 ratio was chosen for the study due to its affordability and adequate solubility characteristics for both the standard and sample components.

Selection of wavelength

Standard solutions of pioglitazone hydrochloride were individually scanned within the 200–400 nm wavelength range. The resulting spectra were overlaid

to analyse the data. Using the selected estimation method, the absorbance wavelength for pioglitazone was selected at 268 nm.

Preparation of solutions

Preparation of Diluent/ Blank

Pioglitazone is practically insoluble in water (low solubility). The mixture of water and acetonitrile in a 60:40 v/v ratio was selected as diluent.

The stock solution is being prepared for pioglitazone

The process began by precisely weighing 37.5 mg of pioglitazone (PIO) and transferring it into a 50 mL volumetric flask. Diluent was added to dissolve the substance, and the mixture was sonicated for 15 minutes to ensure complete dissolution. The solution was then diluted with diluent up to the 50 mL mark. Additionally, carefully pipetted 2.5 mL of the previously created stock solution and transferred into a cleaned and dried 50 mL volumetric flask, diluted with diluent. (37.5 µg/mL of Pioglitazone).

Preparing the sample solution

Weighed equivalent to 150 mg of pioglitazone transferred to a volumetric flask 100 ml volumetric flask that was clean and dry. To fully dissolve all the ingredients, add roughly 70 mL of diluent, sonicated it for up to 30 minutes, adjust the volume with the diluent, and thoroughly mix. After a few minutes of cooling at ambient temperature, strained through a 0.45-micron Nylon filter.

Additionally, carefully pipetted 1 ml of the previously created stock solution and transferred into a volumetric flask 100 ml that has been cleaned and dried, diluted with a diluent. (37.5 µg/ml of Pioglitazone)

Procedure

UV spectrophotometric method was used to analyse standard and sample solutions. The drug content of PIO in tablet samples was evaluated using standard measurements at 268 nm.

Validation of spectroscopic methods

The developed methods were validated following the guidelines established by the International Conference on Harmonization- (ICH) Q2(R2).

Specificity

Specificity testing was performed to identify any potential interactions between the active pharmaceutical ingredient and the excipients used in the tablet formulation. Based on the defined formulation, the excipients were precisely weighed and mixed in appropriate ratios, then diluted using a 60:40 water-acetonitrile solution. The mixture was filtered through a 0.45-micron nylon membrane. Both placebo and standard preparations were then scanned in the UV region to evaluate and compare any interactions between the drug and excipients.

Linearity

Working standard solutions of PIO were transferred into separate 100 ml volumetric flasks in measured aliquots. These were then diluted with diluent to obtain final concentrations of 3.74, 9.35, 18.69, 29.91, 38.38, 44.86 and 56.07 µg/ml. Calibration curves were constructed by plotting absorbance versus concentration, and regression equations were determined for the drug. The concentration range over which PIO followed Beer-Lambert's law was established to be between 3.74 and 56.07 µg/ml.

Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantification (LOQ)

Limit of Detection (LOD)

The limit of detection represents the lowest amount of analyte that can be reliably identified by an analytical method, though it may not always be quantified with full accuracy [12].

LOD can be calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{LOD} = (3.3 \times \sigma) / S,$$

where:

σ is the standard deviation of the response,

S is the slope of the calibration curve corresponding to the analyte.

Limit of Quantification (LOQ)

The limit of quantification refers to the minimum concentration of an analyte that can be measured with acceptable accuracy and precision by the analytical method.

LOQ is commonly expressed by the equation:

$$\text{LOQ} = (10 \times \sigma) / S,$$

where the parameters are the same as defined above.

Accuracy:

Recovery studies were carried out using the standard addition method at three concentration levels 50%, 100%, and 150% to assess the accuracy of the developed method and to examine any potential interference from excipients present in the formulation. The percentage recovery was calculated based on the total amount of drug recovered. For PIO, the recovery values ranged between 98% and 102%. The accuracy of the method was further confirmed by determining the percentage of the added standard PIO recovered using the appropriate calculation formula.

Method Precision

Accuracy in analytical methods refers to the closeness of measured values to the true value across multiple tests conducted on identical homogeneous samples under defined conditions. To assess the repeatability of the method, pioglitazone at a concentration of 37.5 µg/mL was analyzed in six independent trials. The mean absorbance area and the relative standard deviation (% RSD) were calculated. For the method to be considered repeatable, the % RSD should not exceed 2.0%.

Intermediate precision:

Intermediate precision of the assay method was evaluated by performing two separate sets of replicate analyses on different days. The results from the first day were taken from the repeatability study, while the second set of measurements was carried out using a different instrument. For each day's data, the standard deviation (SD), relative standard deviation (RSD), and the difference between mean values were calculated to assess consistency.

Robustness

Robustness evaluates the ability of an analytical method to remain unaffected by small, intentional changes in experimental conditions, reflecting its reliability during routine use. Parameters such as sonication time and wavelength were varied to examine the method's robustness.

RESULTS

A UV spectroscopic estimation method was developed and validated for determining pioglitazone (PIO) in tablet formulations. The method proved to be simple, sensitive, precise, and accurate. The estimation involved measuring the absorbance of the drug at 268 nm. Figure 2,3 illustrates the spectra of blank and PIO respectively. Linearity was confirmed with a correlation coefficient close to 0.999 for PIO over the concentration range of 3.74 (10%) – 56.07(150%) $\mu\text{g/ml}$, as shown in Table 2,3 and with the calibration curve depicted in Figure 4. Calibration graphs were constructed by plotting absorbance against concentration, and least squares regression analysis was used to calculate the slope, intercept, and correlation coefficient at the selected wavelength.

Precision and accuracy were evaluated by calculating the percentage relative standard deviation (% RSD), which complied with ICH guidelines by remaining below 2%. These findings demonstrate excellent repeatability and minimal variability both within and between days, indicating strong method precision and intermediate precision (see Table 4). The suitability of the proposed method was further confirmed by recovery studies, which showed recoveries ranging from 98% to 102%, indicating no interference from tablet excipients (refer to Table 5). Sensitivity was supported by the low values of limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ) reported in Table 3. The method was successfully applied to quantify PIO in three different strengths of tablets (Pioglitazone HCl Tablet containing 7.5 mg, 15 mg and 50 mg of PIO). Analysis of replicate samples yielded assay values between 99% and 101%, confirming the method's reliability for routine pharmaceutical analysis (Table 7). Robustness was assessed by examining % RSD under varied conditions, with results presented in Table 6. Overall, these results demonstrate that the developed method is accurate, precise, user-friendly, and comparable to existing analytical procedures.

Figure 2: spectrum Scan of Blank

Figure 3: spectrum Scan of Pioglitazone

Table 2: Linearity data of PIO

% Level	Conc. ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Mean Absorbance	% RSD
10	3.74	0.068	0.85
25	9.35	0.192	0.30
50	18.69	0.326	0.18
80	29.91	0.522	0.11
100	37.38	0.652	0.09
120	44.86	0.781	0.07
150	56.07	0.970	0.06

Figure 4: Linearity data plot of PIO**Table 3: Results obtained from the statistical analysis**

Active Component	Working range	Correlation coefficient(R^2)	Slope	Y Intercept	LOD ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	LOQ ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)
PIO	10% (3.74 ppm) To 150% (56.07 ppm)	0.999	0.17	0.014	1.95	5.90

Table 4: Method precision and Intermediate precision

Replicates	Method Precision		Intermediate Precision		Cumulative % RSD	Mean % assay value difference
	mg/g	% Assay	mg/g	% Assay		
Sample 1	30.05	100.15	29.96	99.87	100.15	0.06
Sample 2	29.99	99.98	30.14	100.45		
Sample 3	30.22	100.74	30.20	100.68		
Sample 4	30.11	100.35	29.97	99.89		
Sample 5	29.97	99.89	30.04	100.12		
Sample 6	29.99	99.97	29.91	99.70		
Average	30.05	100.18	30.85	100.12		
% RSD	-	0.32	-	0.38		

Table 5: Recovery (Accuracy) results at different concentration levels

Active	Recovery Levels(%)	Mean % Recovery	% RSD	Overall % Recovery
PIO	50	100.5	0.30	100.1
	100	99.8	0.34	
	150	100.2	0.99	

Table 6: Robustness results of PIO

Parameters	PIO Content	
	% Assay	% Difference
As such sample	100.5	-
Change in sonication time Low (20 mintes)	99.7	0.8
Change in sonication time High (40 mintes)	100.0	0.5
Change in wavelength Low (266 nm)	99.5	1.0
Change in wavelength High (270 nm)	99.6	0.9

Table 7: Analysis of PIO tablets (Three different strengths)

Name of the product	Label claim(mg/tab)	Amount found in mg	Percentage label claim(%)
Pioglitazone HCl Tablets 7.5 mg	7.5	7.44	99.2
Pioglitazone HCl Tablets 15 mg	15	14.84	98.9
Pioglitazone HCl Tablets 30 mg	30	30.15	100.5

The UV spectrophotometric method developed for the estimation of pioglitazone hydrochloride (PIO) demonstrated reliable and consistent performance across a concentration range of 3.74–56.07 µg/ml. The method showed strong linearity, with correlation coefficients nearing unity. Precision analysis indicated low relative standard deviation (% RSD) values, reflecting excellent repeatability and minimal intra- and inter-day variability. Accuracy was validated through recovery studies, with results consistently ranging between 98% and 102%. The method also displayed high sensitivity, as evidenced by its low limits of detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ), confirming its effectiveness in detecting small quantities of the analyte. Robustness assessments demonstrated that the method remained stable and dependable under slight variations in experimental conditions. Application of the method to tablet formulations confirmed its ability to accurately quantify the active pharmaceutical ingredient, highlighting its suitability for routine quality control and pharmaceutical analysis.

DISCUSSION

The results of this study hold considerable value for pharmaceutical analysis, especially in the area of diabetes treatment. The development of a UV spectrophotometric method for estimating pioglitazone (PIO) addresses a notable gap in existing literature and introduces a practical approach for analyzing pharmaceutical formulations. By facilitating accurate quantification of active pharmaceutical ingredients, this method improves analytical workflow, supports quality control efforts, and aids in meeting regulatory standards. Its simplicity, sensitivity, and cost-effectiveness further enhance its suitability for routine use in industrial and regulatory laboratory settings. In relation to current research, this method advances analytical practices within the pharmaceutical sciences. Although prior studies have described methods for individual estimation of PIO, this investigation introduces a novel approach for estimating the drug within tablet formulations. This development broadens the range of tools available for ensuring the quality and consistency of pharmaceutical products, offering a more integrated solution for formulation analysis.

Despite its strengths, the study has certain limitations. Additional validation may be necessary to confirm the method's performance across a broader variety of pharmaceutical forms and under different laboratory conditions. Future studies could also explore its application to other drug combinations and assess its robustness in real-world manufacturing environments.

CONCLUSION

The drugs exhibited improved solubility and stability when dissolved in a water: acetonitrile mixture. Favourable regression outcomes at their respective wavelengths confirmed the accuracy of the analytical method. Importantly, the recovery studies highlighted the method's precision in detecting even small variations in drug concentration. Additionally, the low values of LOD and LOQ demonstrated the method's high sensitivity. The proposed method was validated in accordance with ICH guidelines and was found to be simple, rapid, linear, specific, precise, and reproducible. It is well-suited for the routine quantification of PIO in both its pure form and in tablet formulations. Overall, this method provides a reliable, sensitive, accurate, and cost-effective approach for the regular quality assessment of PIO-containing pharmaceutical products.

In conclusion, the UV spectrophotometric method developed in this study offers a significant advancement in pharmaceutical quality analysis. Its accuracy, reliability, and ease of implementation make it a valuable resource for ensuring the quality and regulatory compliance of drug formulations.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

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